

Higher Order Symmetries in Electro-Kinetics and Membrane Parameters†

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Attempts have been made to transcribe higher order coefficients pertaining to electro-kinetic phenomena in terms of known physical parameters; wherefrom higher order symmetries have been found to be explicitly obeyed. A new procedure has been adopted to evaluate the relevant parameters of a composite membrane. Electro-osmotic pressure data have been used for this purpose. The values of various order coefficients obtained from these values of parameters are in comfortable agreement with the experimental ones¹. An expression for evaluating the variation constant of resistivity of a non-ohmic liquid conductor has also been obtained in terms of the physical parameters of the system, which is the first of its kind.

ON SAGER'S reciprocity relation² has been verified in a number of cases³⁻⁵ and now it is more or less recognised as one of the various laws of nature. The same is not the case with higher order symmetries^{6,7} which may be regarded as a logical extension of the first order symmetry. This is because of the lack of their verification on experimental level. The difficulties beset with experiments lie in making precise measurements of highly fine magnitudes which can hardly be accomplished. Their justification on theoretical basis is, however, possible. The present communication aims at such an attempt in the light of classical theory in respect of electro-kinetic phenomena. One very important and interesting aspect of such a study is that it (i) provides a new analytical tool for the evaluation of all the parameters of a composite membrane, (ii) explains the nonlinear thermodynamic higher order coefficients for electro-kinetic phenomena in terms of the known physical parameters, and (iii) suggests an expression for evaluating the variation constant of resistivity of a non-ohmic liquid conductor in terms of the physical parameters of the system hitherto unknown.

Thermodynamic theory of irreversible processes^{8,9} gives the following phenomenological relations in the linear range of electro-kinetic phenomena

$$J = L_{11} \frac{\Delta P}{T} + L_{12} \frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$I = L_{21} \frac{\Delta P}{T} + L_{22} \frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \quad \dots (2)$$

where J and I stand for flow of matter and electricity respectively under the solvodynamic pressure ΔP and electric potential $\Delta \phi$ acting normally across a membrane. T represents the absolute temperature and L_{11} , L_{12} , L_{21} , L_{22} represent phenomenological coefficients.

Viewed from the classical theory L 's are related to the physical parameters of the system as given under :

$$L_{11}/T = \frac{n\pi r^4}{8\eta l}, L_{12}/T = L_{21}/T = \frac{n r^2 \xi D}{4\eta l}, L_{22}/T = \frac{n\pi r^2 k}{l} \quad \dots (3)$$

where n represents the number of capillaries composing the membrane, r and l respectively represent the average radius and average length of each of these capillaries. η , k and D respectively stand for viscosity, specific conductance and dielectric constant of the permeant and ξ denotes the zeta potential at the membrane capillary/permeant interface.

Recently it has been observed^{10,11} that in transport processes the existence of coupling leads to decrease in straight coefficients when restrictions are imposed on fluxes, so that when $I = 0$, we obtain from eqs. (1) and (2)

$$(J)_{I=0} = L_{11} \left(1 - \frac{L_{12}L_{21}}{L_{11}L_{22}} \right) \frac{\Delta P}{T} = L_{11} \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k} \right) \frac{\Delta P}{T} \quad \dots (4)$$

and when $J = 0$

$$(I)_{J=0} = L_{22} \left(1 - \frac{L_{12}L_{21}}{L_{11}L_{22}} \right) \frac{\Delta \phi}{T} = L_{22} \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k} \right) \frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \quad \dots (5)$$

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The quantities in the parentheses in the r.h.s. of eqs. (4) and (5) are the same, positive and less than unity. The relevancy of the above diminution in straight coefficients, may be reviewed from classical aspect as given under :

Absence of either electrical flux or matter flux means that the generation of the flux of a particular kind by some cause is just counteracted by that due to the other one and as such an equivalence may be assumed between the two forces or causes in this situation.

Thus if only flow of matter takes place with the accompanying electrical flux just counterbalanced by the external electrical field or reverse streaming potential (S.P.) it implies that

$$\overrightarrow{\Delta\phi} = \text{S.P.} = \frac{\overleftarrow{\xi D \Delta P}}{4\pi\eta k} \quad \dots (6)$$

Since streaming current is generated by the solvodynamic pressure, a part of the latter equivalent to S.P. is used up in such a process, the magnitude of which is obtained from the following expression for electro-osmotic pressure (E.O.P.)

$$\text{E.O.P.} = \frac{2\xi D}{\pi r^2} \Delta\phi \quad \dots (7)$$

Substitution of $\Delta\phi$ in eq. (7) by S.P. from eq. (6) gives the required equivalent pressure decrease part, $\Delta P'$, of ΔP , the applied solvodynamic pressure as

$$\Delta P' = \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k} \Delta P \quad \dots (8)$$

The net solvodynamic pressure $\Delta P'' = \Delta P - \Delta P'$, therefore, effectively available for solvodynamic transport only is given by

$$\Delta P'' = \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right) \Delta P \quad \dots (9)$$

since solvodynamic and electro-osmotic flows of matter take place independently of each other in wide capillary, compared to double layer thickness, the net flow of matter J may be represented as

$$J = J_S + J_E \quad \dots (10)$$

where J_S represents solvodynamic flow for pressure $\left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right) \Delta P$ and J_E represents electro-osmotic flow of matter due to the streaming current and external electrical potential, i.e., for the net potential

$$\left(\Delta\phi + \frac{\xi D \Delta P}{4\pi\eta k}\right).$$

When $I = 0$, $\overrightarrow{\Delta\phi} = \frac{\overleftarrow{\xi D \Delta P}}{4\pi\eta k}$ so that $J_E = 0$ and

in the linear range

$$(J)_{I=0} = J_S = L_{11} \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right) \frac{\Delta P}{T} \quad \dots (11)$$

which is identical with eq. (4).

On the other hand if the matter flux is made to vanish and only the electrical flux is allowed to be transported it means that the electro-osmotic flow is just counterbalanced by the solvodynamic flow and, therefore, in view of eq. (9)

$$\left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right) \Delta\phi = \frac{2\xi D}{\pi r^2} \left(\Delta\phi - \frac{\xi D}{4\pi\eta k} \Delta P\right),$$

(as streaming potential acts in opposition to the applied potential), or

$$\overrightarrow{\Delta P} = \frac{2\xi D}{\pi r^2} \overleftarrow{\Delta\phi},$$

so that

$$\text{S.P.} = \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k} \Delta\phi \quad \dots (12)$$

The net flow of current I thus depends on the net potential $\left(\Delta\phi - \frac{\xi^2 D^2 \Delta\phi}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right)$ and in the linear range we may write

$$(I)_{J=0} = L_{22} \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right) \frac{\Delta\phi}{T} \quad \dots (13)$$

which conforms to eq. (5).

The relevancy of the diminution of straight coefficients is thus simple and straightforward.

In case both the fluxes are non-zero, the net flow of matter J and electrical current I in the linear range will be represented by eqs. (1) and (2) respectively.

We now proceed to discuss the non-linear range of the fluxes. For an effective pressure ΔP Poiseuille's equation for a composite membrane may be written as

$$\Delta P = \frac{8\eta l}{\pi n r^4} J_S + \frac{\rho}{n^2 \pi^2 r^4} J_S^2 \quad \dots (14)$$

where ρ is the density of the permeant. On rearrangement we obtain

$$\frac{8\eta l J_S}{\pi n r^4} = \Delta P \left(1 + \frac{\rho J_S}{8n\pi\eta l}\right)^{-1} \approx \Delta P \left(1 - \frac{\rho J_S}{8n\pi\eta l}\right)$$

provided $(\rho J_S / 8n\pi\eta l) < 1$ which is satisfied in the case of a composite membrane¹ of very fine porosity.

J_S is, therefore, obtained as

$$J_S = \frac{n\pi r^4}{8\eta l} \Delta P \left(1 + \frac{\rho r^4 \Delta P}{8^2 \eta^2 l^2}\right)^{-1}$$

$$= \frac{n\pi r^4}{8\eta l} (\Delta P) - \frac{n\pi r^8 \rho}{8^3 \eta^3 l^3} (\Delta P)^2 + \frac{n\pi r^{12} \rho^2}{8^5 \eta^5 l^5} (\Delta P)^3 \dots \quad (15)$$

when $(\rho r^4 \Delta P / 8^2 \eta^2 l^2) < 1$ which holds upto $\Delta P = 10^5$ dyne for membranes of our interest. Replacing ΔP in this equation by E.O.P. from eq. (7), we obtain electro-osmotic flow J_E as

$$J_E = \frac{n r^2 \xi D}{4 \eta l} (\Delta \varphi) - \frac{n r^4 \rho \xi^2 D^2}{2.8^2 \pi^2 \eta^3 l^3} (\Delta \varphi)^2 + \frac{n r^6 \rho^2 \xi^3 D^3}{8^4 \pi^2 \eta^5 l^5} ((\Delta \varphi)^3) \dots \quad (16)$$

which is related to the current flow I , for the same potential $\Delta \varphi$ as

$$\frac{J_E}{I} = \frac{\xi D}{4 \pi \eta k} \quad \text{or} \quad I = \frac{4 \pi \eta k}{\xi D} J_E \quad \dots \quad (17)$$

Since electrical flux I is accompanied with the electro-osmotic matter flux J_E it is quite likely that current flow has to overcome the viscous force as well in addition to the electrical resistance. This is well predicted by eq. (17).

In view of these equations, namely, (15)–(17) we obtain expressions for J and I under the conditions (a) when one of the fluxes is zero and (b) when none of the fluxes is zero.

In case $I = 0$, the expression for $(J)_{I=0}$ in eq. (11) assumes the following form in power series of ΔP

$$(J)_{I=0} = \frac{n\pi r^4}{8\eta l} \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right) (\Delta P) - \frac{n\pi r^8 \rho}{8^3 \eta^3 l^3}$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right)^2 (\Delta P)^2 + \frac{n\pi r^{12} \rho^2}{8^5 \eta^5 l^5} \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right)^3 (\Delta P)^3 \dots \quad (18)$$

Replacing $\Delta \phi$ in eq. (16) by $\left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right) \Delta \phi$ and multiplying with $\frac{4\pi\eta k}{\xi D}$, $(I)_{J=0}$ is obtained as

$$(I)_{J=0} = \frac{n\pi r^2 k}{l} \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right) (\Delta \phi)$$

$$- \frac{n\pi r^2 k}{l} \cdot \frac{\rho r^2 \xi D}{4.8\pi \eta^2 l^2} \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right)^2 (\Delta \phi)^2$$

$$+ \frac{n\pi r^2 k}{l} \cdot \frac{\rho^2 r^4 \xi^2 D^2}{4^2.8^2 \pi^2 \eta^4 l^4} \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k}\right)^3 (\Delta \phi)^3 \dots \quad (19)$$

which represents the non-linear form of eq. (13) in power series of $\Delta \phi$. Eq. (19) is identical with the

corresponding expression for the flow of current through a non-ohmic conductor. Resistance, R , of such a system varies with the increase of e.m.f. and may be represented¹¹ as

$$R = R_0(1 + \alpha \Delta \phi) \quad \dots \quad (20)$$

where R_0 and α are, respectively, the resistance at zero e.m.f. and a constant so that current I may be given by

$$I = \frac{(\Delta \phi)}{R_0} - \frac{\alpha (\Delta \phi)^2}{R_0} + \frac{\alpha^2 (\Delta \phi)^3}{R_0} \quad \dots \quad (21)$$

provided $\alpha \Delta \phi < 1$. Comparing eqs. (19) and (21) we find that

$$R_0 = \frac{l}{n\pi r^2 k} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha = \frac{\rho r^2 \xi D}{4.8\pi \eta^2 l^2} \quad \dots \quad (22)$$

α thus seems to have a meaning in terms of the parameters of the system concerned, which is the first of its kind and can be evaluated experimentally.

When both the fluxes are non-zero the net potential and pressure present in the system are $[(\Delta \phi + (\xi D \Delta P / 4\pi \eta k)]$ and $\{1 - (\xi^2 D^2 / 2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k)\} \Delta P$ respectively. Hence in view of eq. (10) the net flow of matter J is obtained as

$$J = \frac{n\pi r^4}{8\eta l} (\Delta P) + \frac{n r^2 \xi D}{4\eta l} (\Delta \phi)$$

$$- \frac{1}{2!} \frac{n\pi r^8 \rho}{4.8^2 \eta^3 l^3} \left(1 - \frac{\xi^2 D^2}{\pi^2 r^2 \eta k} + \frac{\xi^4 D^4}{2\pi^4 r^4 \eta^2 k^2}\right) (\Delta P)^2$$

$$- \frac{n r^4 \rho \xi^3 D^3}{4.8^2 \pi^2 \eta^4 k l^3} (\Delta P) (\Delta \phi) - \frac{1}{2!} \frac{n r^4 \rho \xi^2 D^2}{8^2 \pi \eta^3 l^3} (\Delta \phi)^2$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2!} \frac{3n\pi r^{12} \rho^2}{2.8^4 \eta^5 l^5} \left(1 - \frac{3\xi^2 D^2}{2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k} + \frac{3\xi^4 D^4}{4\pi^4 r^4 \eta^2 k^2}\right) (\Delta P)^3$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2!} \frac{3n r^6 \rho^2 \xi^5 D^5}{8^5 \pi^4 \eta^7 k^2 l^5} (\Delta P)^2 (\Delta \phi)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2!} \frac{3n r^6 \rho^2 \xi^4 D^4}{2.8^4 \pi^3 \eta^6 k l^5} (\Delta P) (\Delta \phi)^2$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2!} \frac{3n r^6 \rho^2 \xi^3 D^3}{4.8^3 \pi^2 \eta^5 l^5} (\Delta \phi)^3 \quad \dots \quad (23)$$

substitution of $\{1 - (\xi^2 D^2 / 2\pi^2 r^2 \eta k)\} \Delta \phi$ in eq. (19) by $\left(\Delta \phi + \frac{\xi D \Delta P}{4\pi \eta k}\right)$ the net flow of current I is obtained as

$$I = \frac{n r^2 \xi D}{4\eta l} (\Delta P) + \frac{n\pi r^2 k}{l} (\Delta \phi)$$

$$- \frac{1}{2!} \frac{n r^4 \rho \xi^3 D^3}{4.8^2 \pi^2 \eta^4 k l^3} (\Delta P)^2 - \frac{n r^4 \xi^2 D^2}{8^2 \pi \eta^3 l^3} (\Delta P) (\Delta \phi)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\frac{1}{2!} \frac{rm^4 \rho \xi D k}{2.8 \eta^2 l^3} (\Delta\phi)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} \frac{3nr^6 \rho^2 \xi^5 D^5}{8^3 \pi^4 \eta^7 k^2 l^5} (\Delta P)^3 \\
 & + \frac{1}{2!} \frac{3nr^6 \rho^2 \xi^4 D^4}{2.8^4 \pi^3 \eta^6 k l^5} (\Delta P)^2 (\Delta\phi) \\
 & + \frac{1}{2!} \frac{3nr^6 \rho^2 \xi^3 D^3}{4.8^3 \pi^2 \eta^5 l^5} (\Delta P) (\Delta\phi)^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} \frac{3nr^6 \rho^2 \xi^2 D^2 k}{8^3 \pi \eta^4 l^5} (\Delta\phi)^3 \quad \dots (24)
 \end{aligned}$$

If subscripts 1 and 2 be used for matter flow and electrical flow respectively then from eqs. (23) and (24) we obtain the following equalities in terms of L 's as used in irreversible thermodynamics

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{12} &= L_{21} = \frac{nr^2 \xi D}{4\eta l} \\
 L_{112} &= L_{211} = -\frac{nr^4 \rho \xi^3 D^3}{4.8^2 \pi^2 \eta^4 k l^3} \\
 L_{122} &= L_{212} = -\frac{nr^4 \rho \xi^2 D^2}{8^2 \pi \eta^3 l^3} \\
 L_{1112} &= L_{2111} = \frac{3nr^6 \rho^2 \xi^5 D^5}{8^3 \pi^4 \eta^7 k^2 l^5} \\
 L_{1122} &= L_{2112} = \frac{3nr^6 \rho^2 \xi^4 D^4}{2.8^4 \pi^3 \eta^6 k l^5} \\
 L_{1222} &= L_{2122} = \frac{3nr^6 \rho^2 \xi^3 D^3}{4.8^3 \pi^2 \eta^5 l^5}
 \end{aligned}$$

The higher order symmetries are thus found to be observed like the first order symmetry of Onsager.

Membrane parameters

We now proceed to obtain the parameters of a composite membrane by making use of electro-osmotic pressure data. For the electro-osmotic flow of matter J_E we have

$$\text{E.O.P.} = \frac{2\xi D}{\pi r^2} \Delta\phi = \frac{8\eta l}{n\pi r^4} J_E + \frac{\rho}{n^2 \pi^2 r^4} J_E^2 \quad \dots (25)$$

The first term of the r.h.s. of this equation is that due to the viscous effect and the second due to kinetic energy term. Since in all practical measurements of E.O.P. kinetic energy term is not realised the experimental value of E.O.P. is, therefore, always less than the expected one. From eq. (16) we therefore, obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\text{E.O.P.})_{obs} &= \frac{8\eta l}{n\pi r^4} J_E = \frac{2\xi D}{\pi r^2} (\Delta\phi) - \frac{\rho \xi^2 D^2}{16\pi^2 \eta^2 l^2} (\Delta\phi)^2 \\
 &+ \frac{\rho^2 r^2 \xi^3 D^3}{4.8^2 \pi^3 \eta^4 l^4} (\Delta\phi)^3 \quad \dots (26)
 \end{aligned}$$

Retaining terms upto the second power of $\Delta\phi$ only we get

$$\frac{(\text{E.O.P.})_{obs}}{\Delta\phi} = \frac{2\xi D}{\pi r^2} - \frac{\rho \xi^2 D^2}{16\pi^2 \eta^2 l^2} \Delta\phi. \quad \dots (27)$$

This is an equation of a straight line with intercept $= \frac{2\xi D}{\pi r^2}$ and a slope $= \frac{\rho \xi^2 D^2}{16\pi^2 \eta^2 l^2}$. Thus the average values of r and l are obtained as follows

$$r = \left(\frac{2\xi D}{\pi \times \text{intercept}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (28)$$

$$l = \frac{\xi D}{4\pi \eta} \left(\frac{\rho}{\text{slope}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (29)$$

Our expression for ' r ', thus obtained, agrees with that¹² of Rastogi *et al.* following altogether a different procedure. The present procedure, however, has one advantage over the earlier one in as much as it provides a method for the estimation of the average pore length, l , of the membrane capillaries directly from the analysis of the electro-osmotic pressure data.

In order to assess the correctness and practicability of the above analysis we have examined the recent E.O.P. data of Rastogi, Singh and Srivastava¹. Electro-osmotic pressure per unit volt applied has been plotted against the applied electrical potential in the system. A straight line has been obtained in accordance with eq. (27). This has been shown in Fig. 1 for composite membranes¹ IV and V.

Fig. 1. Plots of E.O.P./ $\Delta\phi$ Vs. $\Delta\phi$, for Acetone/Pyrex system.

Substitution of $\xi = 0.07$ volt, $\rho = 0.7742$ gm./ml., as used by Rastogi *et al.*, and the literature values¹ of $D = 20.7$ and $\eta = 0.003$ poise and $k = 2 \times 10^{-3}$ mhos/cm. for the permeant acetone we have obtained r and l using eqs. (28) and (29) together with the values of the intercepts and slopes for composite membranes nos. IV and V comprising acetone/pyrex

sinter system. Putting the values of r and l thus obtained in the expressions for L_{11}/T or L_{12}/T as given in eq. (3) we obtain n . The values of l and n thus obtained, differ considerably from the previous values¹ as will be evident from Table 1. The difference appears to be due to the arbitrary choice of the

had there been very accurate experimental values of these higher order coefficients available. Unfortunately it is not possible since this requires measurement of very high precession on the experimental level which can hardly be achieved in the laboratory at present. The present agreement,

TABLE 1—COMPARATIVE VALUES OF MEMBRANE PARAMETERS AS OBTAINED FROM PRESENT AND PREVIOUS^{1,2} METHODS

Membrane	Parameters							
	from present considerations				from previous considerations			
	n	l (cm)	r (cm)	r/l	n	l (cm)	r (cm)	r/l
IV	1.07×10^8	1.34×10^{-3}	3.4×10^{-4}	2.54×10^{-1}	3.2×10^8	3×10^{-1}	3.2×10^{-4}	1.06×10^{-3}
V	1.48×10^8	1.22×10^{-3}	2.9×10^{-4}	2.34×10^{-1}	2.4×10^8	3×10^{-1}	3.4×10^{-4}	1.13×10^{-3}

TABLE 2—EVALUATION OF THE VARIOUS ORDER PHENOMENOLOGICAL COEFFICIENTS FROM THE PRESENT AND THE PREVIOUS^{1,2} PARAMETERS

Coefficients	Membrane					
	IV			V		
	Observed	Calculated from present parameters	Calculated from previous parameters	Observed	Calculated from present parameters	Calculated from previous parameters
L_{11}/T (cm. ⁵ dyn. ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹)	1.1×10^{-8}	1.1×10^{-8}	1.5×10^{-8}	1.1×10^{-8}	1.1×10^{-8}	1.4×10^{-8}
L_{12}/T (cm. ³ sec. ⁻¹ V ⁻²)	1.07×10^{-4}	1.1×10^{-4}	1.5×10^{-4}	0.97×10^{-4}	1.3×10^{-4}	1.2×10^{-4}
L_{111}/T^2 (cm. ⁷ sec. ⁻¹ dyn. ⁻²)	—	9.5×10^{-12}	2.5×10^{-14}	—	7.9×10^{-12}	3.8×10^{-16}
L_{112}/T^2 (cm. ⁵ sec. ⁻¹ dyn. ⁻¹ V ⁻¹)	13.1×10^{-10}	4.6×10^{-10}	10.3×10^{-13}	12.1×10^{-10}	4.3×10^{-10}	9.2×10^{-15}
L_{122}/T^2 (cm. ³ sec. ⁻¹ V ⁻²)	10.7×10^{-8}	21.7×10^{-8}	4.8×10^{-10}	12.0×10^{-8}	20.0×10^{-8}	4.3×10^{-12}
L_{1111}/T^3 (cm. ⁹ sec. ⁻¹ dyn. ⁻³)	—	8.1×10^{-16}	2.1×10^{-28}	—	1.7×10^{-16}	3.6×10^{-26}
L_{1112}/T^3 (cm. ⁷ sec. ⁻¹ dyn. ⁻² V ⁻¹)	7.0×10^{-15}	2.8×10^{-15}	10.6×10^{-26}	1.4×10^{-14}	2.1×10^{-15}	10.3×10^{-25}
L_{1122}/T^3 (cm. ⁵ sec. ⁻¹ dyn. ⁻¹ V ⁻²)	6.68×10^{-12}	1.3×10^{-12}	5.0×10^{-22}	9.96×10^{-12}	10.0×10^{-15}	4.8×10^{-22}
L_{1222}/T^3 (cm. ³ sec. ⁻¹ V ⁻³)	—	6.0×10^{-10}	2.3×10^{-19}	—	4.7×10^{-10}	2.3×10^{-19}

previous workers¹ in correlating the average length of a composite membrane to its thickness. It is quite likely that the porosity of the channels acting as passage for transport in membranes may not be uniform from one end to the other. The permeation of matter in the steady state, will, therefore, be virtually controlled by those parts in a channel which have minimum aperture and the effective average length and radius will be determined by those of a single such narrowest paths. Thus r and l are expected to have more or less a comparable magnitude, as in the present case. It is gratifying to note that the correctness of the values of the parameters obtained in the present case is well exhibited by the fair agreement of the experimental and the theoretically calculated values of the higher order coefficients involving different higher powers of the parameters where the magnitude and order of the error in ' n ' cannot be evenly compensated by those of ' l '. It may be emphasised here that the agreement might have been all the more comforting

in spite of this disadvantage, is, therefore, very much heartening and lends support to our formalism unambiguously. On the other hand the values of parameters obtained from previous considerations based on the expressions for first order coefficients give such values of higher order coefficients which are in complete disagreement with the experimental ones because in those cases the order of error in n is not evenly compensated by that of l . This is evident from Table 2.

It is to be noted here that the values of η and D for a permeant in the double layer may be different from that in the bulk but in the absence of any available precise values of these in the double layer the use of the bulk values has been the accepted procedure^{1,2}. Further since in the present case we are interested only in the workable average values of the parameters of a composite membrane the use of the bulk values of η and D would not be unjustified.

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